

Engineering Coupled Consortia-Based Biosensors for Diagnostic

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Abstract

Synthetic multicellular systems have great potential for performing complex tasks, including multi-signal detection and computation through cell-to-cell communication. However, engineering these systems is challenging, requiring precise control over the cell concentrations of distinct members and coordination of their activity. Here, we develop a bacterial consortia-based biosensor for Heme and Lactate, wherein members are coupled through a global shared quorum-sensing signal that simultaneously controls the activity of the diverse biosensing strains. The multicellular system incorporates a gene circuit that computes the minimum between each biosensor’s activity and the shared signal. We evaluate three consortia configurations: one where the shared signal is externally supplied, another directly produced via an inducible gene circuit, and a third generated through an incoherent feedforward loop (IFFL) gene circuit. Among these configurations, the IFFL system, which maintains the shared signal at low and stable levels over an extended period, demonstrates improved performance and robustness against perturbations in cell populations. Finally, we examine these coupled consortia to monitor Lactate and Heme in humanized fecal samples for diagnostics.

Introduction

Engineered multicellular systems harness the diverse abilities of individual populations, enabling cooperative interactions to accomplish complex tasks across various applications, including bioproduction [1], healthcare [2], and environmental monitoring [3]. For instance, synthetic consortia have been developed to address challenges in bacterial biosensor performance, including enhancing multi-target detection [4] and minimizing crosstalk between analytes [5], [6]. These tasks often require large-scale gene circuits, which, when carried out by a single strain, can impose a burden on gene expression and deplete vital resources [7], [8]. Moreover, bacterial biosensors often undergo genetic modifications, such as removing essential genes or adding genes to improve sensing sensitivity [9]. However, combining these modifications within a single strain can result in crosstalk among diverse biological processes [10]. By distributing complex genetic pathways across multiple species, synthetic consortia can alleviate this burden, enhancing overall functionality and reducing strain-specific limitations [6], [11].

Despite significant progress in engineering synthetic microbial consortia, further advancements in their design are still required [12]. In synthetic consortia, individual members are often uncoupled and function

40 independently within the network [13], leading to challenges such as output misinterpretation [14], as the
41 observed output is influenced not only by the intended activity of each member (f_i) but also by their cell
42 concentrations (N_i) ($Out \propto \sum_{i=1}^M N_i \cdot f_i$) (Fig. 1a) ('Analog Signal Control in Biosensor Consortia' section
43 in Methods). Proper operation of uncoupled consortia requires maintaining a balance in the cell
44 concentrations of the different members over time—a task that becomes increasingly challenging in
45 complex environments [15]. In contrast, coupled consortia, meaning each member is aware of the presence
46 and activity of the others, an optimized design can be achieved [4], [11], [16], [17], [18], [19]. Such
47 consortia, where members are linked and their activities are coordinated, could exhibit reduced dependency
48 on individual cell concentrations, resulting in more robust system performance against the perturbations of
49 cell concentration ('Mathematical Modelling for Signal Coupling in Microbial Consortia' in Methods) [20].

50 Coupled consortia can be established using either a negative feedback loop to maintain cell concentrations
51 at specific levels [21] or through indirect interactions where cells compete for a shared activation source
52 (Fig. 1a) [22]. In this study, we focused on indirect interactions by simultaneously activating the different
53 biosensors within the consortia using shared signaling molecules (S_T). Coupling among consortia members
54 occurs when the concentration of the shared signaling molecule is lower than the total cell population ($S_T <$
55 $\sum_{i=1}^M N_i$), ensuring the activity of the consortia members is governed by the availability of the shared signal
56 rather than their population size. In this scenario, the shared signal acts as a limiting factor for activation of
57 the various biosensor strains, rather than the cell density. This coupling, in turn, minimizes the impact of
58 fluctuations and perturbations in individual member cell concentrations on the overall consortia's output
59 (Fig. 1b and the section 'Mathematical Modelling for Signal Coupling in Microbial Consortia' in Materials
60 and Methods). Furthermore, when the shared signal is inducible, it functions as an enabling signal for the
61 consortium-based biosensor [23], allowing signal transmission when the external inducer is high and
62 blocking transmission when the inducer is low.

63 For biological systems with an analog response, such as bacterial biosensors, the enable signal's mechanism
64 can be implemented by a genetic circuit that computes the minimum (MIN) between the shared signaling
65 molecules (S_T) and the biosensor response activity (Supplementary Fig. 1 and 'Designing and Modeling of
66 a Bioluminescent *luxCDABE* Cassette' in Supplementary Methods). In this design (Fig. 1b), where S_T
67 simultaneously facilitates coupling and enabling between consortia members, programming its appropriate
68 ON and OFF levels (S_{T_ON} and S_{T_OFF}) presents a significant challenge. The concentration of these
69 molecules must be lower than the total cell concentration to couple the cells effectively, yet higher than the
70 activity of each biosensor to accurately compute the minimum operation (Eq. 20 and the section 'Analog
71 Signal Control in Biosensor Consortia' in Methods). To address this challenge, we implemented an
72 incoherent type-1 feedforward loop (IFFL) to regulate the synthesis of the shared signal due to the network's
73 ability to maintain the signal stable at low levels for an extended period, e.g., spanning more than 15 hours
74 in laboratory condition (LB medium). In the IFFL circuit, the input simultaneously activates and, through
75 an intermediary molecule, inhibits the output protein, either a reporter protein or catalyst for synthesizing
76 quorum-sensing (QS) signals that serve as shared signals ('Conceptual and Mathematical Examination of
77 the IFFL Network Dynamics' in Methods) [24], [25], [26], [27], [28]. The IFFL circuit generates a shared
78 signal that efficiently manages biosensor information, coupling the activities of bacterial consortia and
79 integrating diverse cellular data, thereby ensuring the functionality of the collective system.

80 This study involves three consortia configurations for simultaneously detecting Heme and Lactate (Fig. 1b).
81 The first configuration, termed the "IFFL Network System," consists of three strains: two strains dedicated
82 to detecting the Heme and Lactate biomarkers, respectively and a third strain responsible for producing the
83 QS shared signal at low levels via an IFFL network. The second configuration, termed the "Direct
84 Regulation System," is similar to the first, but the shared signal is generated at high levels through a

85 transcriptional cascade of two layers. Both configurations generate the shared CHL signal, but their
86 underlying network architectures differ. Finally, the third configuration, termed the "External Induction
87 System," consists of Heme and Lactate bacterial biosensors where the shared signal is externally supplied
88 once. The purpose of this configuration is to compare the effects of signal production by a bacterial strain
89 with the direct external addition of the shared signal on the consortia output. Additionally, it enables an
90 assessment of how different concentrations of the shared signal influence system performance. Heme is
91 associated with bleeding [29], [30], often accompanied by unhealthy conditions such as inflammatory
92 bowel disease (IBD), various types of colitis (e.g., ischemic colitis, infectious colitis), and neoplasia [31].
93 Lactate is associated with IBD [32], [33], colorectal cancer (CRC) [34], [35], and lactic acidosis [34]. Both
94 molecules can be identified in the feces of patients experiencing inflammation. In summary, we evaluated
95 the performance of three synthetic consortia for detecting Heme and Lactate, with the IFFL demonstrating
96 better performance.

97 Results

98 Synthetic IFFL network

99 An IFFL motif (Fig. 2a) consists of three components: an initial regulator (X) that directly activates the
100 target gene (Z) and indirectly represses it through an intermediate regulator (Y). IFFL motifs are commonly
101 observed in natural gene networks and have been integrated into many synthetic biological systems, with a
102 range of functionalities, including pulse generation [36], [37], amplitude band-pass filtering [38], [39],
103 response time acceleration [40], [41], perfect adaptation and dosage gene stability [37], [42], fold change
104 detection in input signals [43], [44], and analog-to-digital data conversion [45]. In this study, we engineered
105 the IFFL circuit to exhibit sustained plateau-like stability. To achieve such behavior, our simulation results
106 indicate that the IFFL network (Fig. 2c) should be programmed so that the repression pathway (R) is weaker
107 than the activation pathway (A) ('Conceptual and Mathematical Examination of the IFFL Network
108 Dynamics' in Methods). In this specific design, called plateau-like output ($k_n = 1.50$, red curve; $k_n =$
109 0.5 , blue curve in Fig. 2c), the initial rise in output is driven by direct activation. Subsequently, after a time
110 delay, repression begins to compensate for the activation, resulting in a stable output and an earlier transition
111 to a steady state. In contrast, in the pulse-like output design ($k_n = 0.01$, Fig. 2c green curve), when
112 repression is more dominant, the signal decreases to its baseline state following the initial stimulus. Here,
113 the k_n parameter quantifies the relative strength between the activation and repression pathways. A larger
114 value of k_n means activation is more dominant in the process ('Conceptual and Mathematical Examination
115 of the IFFL Network Dynamics' in Methods).

116 To experimentally implement such an IFFL network (Fig. 2a), we utilized genetic circuits, which are
117 triggered by Acyl Homoserine Lactones 3OC6HSL (AHL) [46]. The AHL molecules bind to the *LuxR*
118 activating $P_{\text{lux(LBL)}}$, a low basal level (LBL) P_{lux} promoter. This promoter is designed to lower its basal
119 activity and extend the time required to achieve steady-state expression [45]. In turn, the $P_{\text{lux(LBL)}}$ governs
120 two distinct pathways: *ExsA*, directly activating the super-fold green fluorescent protein fused with the *ssrA*
121 degradation tag (*sfGFP*), and T7 RNA polymerase (*T7 RNAP*) [47], initiating the anti-activator *ExsD*.
122 Specifically, we selected *ExsD* to shunt *ExsA* from binding to the P_{ex} promoter, which activates the *sfGFP*
123 expression. In the regulatory mechanism of *P. aeruginosa*'s Type Three Secretion System (TTSS), two
124 proteins, *ExsA* and *ExsD*, play pivotal roles in linking transcription with secretion. *ExsA* acts as an essential
125 transcriptional activator necessary for expressing the complete set of TTSS genes [48], [49]. On the other
126 hand, *ExsD* functions as an anti-activator to balance the activity of *ExsA* [50]. The *sfGFP* is fused with a
127 *ssrA* degradation tag, shortening its half-life. The selection of *sfGFP-ssrA* ensures that the kinetics of the
128 fluorescent protein would have minimized the impact on the overall response time of the genetic circuit.

129 We also constructed a direct regulation circuit (Fig. 2b) comprising only the activation pathway (A) of the
130 IFFL network through a two-layer genetic cascade.

131 We recorded the time-response characteristic (GFP/OD_{600}) of both the IFFL network and direct regulation
132 circuit for about 30 hours, each activated by the inducer AHL at the initial time (Fig. 2d). The GFP/OD_{600}
133 measurements represent population-level data normalized per cell. An IFFL-based gene circuit can maintain
134 the production at constant low levels for an extended period (Fig. 2d, red curve), spanning over 15 hours,
135 while direct regulation results show an increase in the GFP/OD_{600} levels over time (Fig. 2d, black curve).
136 Using the mean value of the IFFL experimental data curve between 2 to 15 hours (Fig. 2d, vertical black
137 dashed line), the variance between the experimental data and the average line exhibited less than a 20%
138 fluctuation (Supplementary Fig. 2), suggesting a stable expression over this time. To compare with the
139 simulation output (Fig. 2c), we also present the normalized signal relative to its maximum level Z/Z_{max} ,
140 demonstrating that the IFFL network achieves a steady state at least three times faster than direct regulation
141 (Supplementary Fig. 3). Here, the response time refers to the duration required for the circuit to reach its
142 steady state. Additionally, when we constructed a new IFFL circuit (Supplementary Fig. 4) with a different
143 repression pathway compared to the activation pathways (i.e., k_n around 0.2), we experimentally observed
144 a pulse-like behavior rather than a stable signal, consistent with our simulation results (Fig. 2c).

145 In the direct regulation circuit, we observed a consistent rise in the output over time (Fig. 2d, black curve),
146 lasting approximately 30 hours without reaching saturation. A simpler version of the direct regulation
147 circuit, including a single-layer gene circuit, was also constructed and tested (Supplementary Fig. 5).
148 Notably, the absence of the *exsA* gene in this circuit did not accelerate the process of reaching a steady state.
149 When the circuit was induced with a low AHL concentration (3 nM), it reached a steady state after 13 hours.
150 This suggests that lowering the AHL concentration may help accelerate the steady-state process in the direct
151 regulation system. However, this simpler direct regulation circuit presents challenges as the P_{lux} promoter
152 does not operate at its ON binary level [44], making the system highly sensitive to AHL fluctuations
153 (Supplementary Fig. 6).

154 Comparing the growth rates (OD_{600}) of cells from the IFFL network and direct regulation circuit, the IFFL
155 network reaches a higher cell concentration (Fig. 2d, inset). This result suggests that the IFFL network
156 utilizes fewer resources in the same environment and potentially performs better in resource-limited
157 settings. Moreover, the dynamic response of the IFFL circuit demonstrates reduced stability after 15 hours
158 as the cells enter the stationary phase ($OD_{600} > 1$, Supplementary Fig. 7). To validate this, we conducted
159 experiments (Supplementary Figs. 8-10) that maintained the OD_{600} of the IFFL network and direct
160 regulation circuit in their exponential growth phase for an extended period of approximately 24.5 hours
161 (Supplementary Fig. 8). These results indicated that the IFFL circuit exhibited stability over this extended
162 period (Supplementary Figs. 8-9). Finally, we tested both circuits in M9 media supplemented with 0.4%
163 glucose, where they reached the stationary phase earlier than in LB, resulting in shorter stability period
164 compared to in LB media (Supplementary Fig. 10).

165 Whole-cell biosensors

166 The IFFL network demonstrated long-term (e.g., a couple of days) stability and low output expression,
167 making it ideally suited to serve as a signal for cohesively integrating the activity of biosensors within
168 consortia. According to our model (Eq. 20 in section 'Mathematical Modelling for Signal Coupling in
169 Microbial Consortia' in Methods), when the concentration of the shared signal is lower than the total cell
170 concentration, a coupling between the cells is established. Furthermore, maintaining a consistent signal
171 over time across multiple bacterial biosensors ensures a uniform impact of the shared signal on their output.

172 To evaluate the stability signal with the bacterial biosensors, we created four strains: two of these strains
173 are activated by AHL and produce an orthogonal QS cell-cell signaling molecule acyl-homoserine lactone
174 3OHC14:1-HSL (CHL), one through direct regulation (Fig. 3a) and the other through IFFL network (Fig.
175 3b). For both strains, we replaced the sfGFP, as shown in Fig. 2b and 2a, with *CinI* (Figs. 3a and 3b). The
176 *CinI* serves as an enzyme responsible for catalyzing the synthesis of CHL, which then distributes throughout
177 the media and diffuses into the consortia wiring Heme and Lactate-responsive biosensor strain's activities
178 (Fig. 3). The CHL molecule functions as a shared signal to couple the other members within the consortia.
179 The third and fourth strains include a genetic circuit that computes a minimum operation ('Designing and
180 Modeling of a Bioluminescent luxCDABE Cassett' in Supplementary Methods) between the responses of
181 CHL and either Heme (Fig. 3c) or Lactate (Fig. 3d). The minimum operation circuit was implemented by
182 reengineering the bioluminescent *luxCDABE* reporter [49]. In this system, the *luxAB* genes, encoding the
183 luciferase subunits responsible for catalyzing the luminescence reaction, are regulated by the CHL, while
184 the *luxCDE* genes, encoding the fatty acid reductase complex required for synthesizing the fatty aldehyde
185 substrate, are controlled by either the Heme- or Lactate-responsive pathways [51]. When the *luxAB* and
186 *luxCDE* are divided and regulated by two distinct inputs, the bioluminescent signal (I) is described by $I \propto$
187 $MIN \left\{ \frac{g(LuxAB)}{K_R}, \frac{h(luxCDE)}{K_F} \right\}$, where g is a function of LuxA and LuxB concentrations, h is a function of
188 LuxC, LuxD, and LuxE concentrations, and K_R and K_F are the reverse and forward rates of the
189 bioluminescent reaction ('Designing and Modeling of a Bioluminescent luxCDABE Cassett' in
190 Supplementary Methods), respectively [52]. Notably, the minimum operation (MIN) functions as an AND
191 logic gate when applied to binary inputs [0,1]. For example, when both the CHL and Heme or Lactate-
192 responsive pathways are activated, then the system would go into the 'ON' state. In contrast, it remains an
193 'OFF' state when only one or none of the pathways is activated (Supplementary Fig. 11). For the Heme-
194 responsive strain, the *Lactococcus lactis* Heme-responsive transcriptional repressor *HrtR* and an outer-
195 membrane transporter *ChuA* are expressed under constitutive promoters P_{rod} and P_{J23107} , respectively, which
196 are located on an MCP. Extracellular Heme enters bacterial cells through the outer-membrane transporter
197 *ChuA* and interacts with the transcriptional repressor *HrtR* to allow for the expression of *LuxCDE* genes.
198 The Heme input regulates *luxCDE* genes via the Heme-sensitive promoter $P_{L(HrtO)}$, which is located on an
199 HCP. For the Lactate-responsive strain, the CHL-responsive pathway is the same as the Heme-responsive
200 strain, which is also located on LCP. The Lactate-responsive pathway contains the constitutive production
201 (P_{rod}) of an *LldR* repressor, which is located on MCP. Transcriptional regulation in *E. coli* in response to
202 Lactate involves the Lactate-sensing transcription factor *LldR*, a member of the *GntR* family. *LldR* is
203 capable of sensing Lactate [53]. It derepresses the P_{LldR} promoter and activates the expression of *LuxCDE*
204 in the presence of Lactate, located on the HCP.

205 Next, we explored the dynamic interaction between the two strains in a co-culture environment. For Heme-
206 responsive strain co-culture (Figs. 3e and 3f); either the direct regulation circuit (Fig. 3a) or the stability
207 output IFFL network (Fig. 3b) was combined with the Heme-responsive strain (Fig. 3c) at a chosen 1:1
208 ratio in volume. The experiments were conducted with AHL at a concentration of 2 μ M and Heme at 2 μ M.
209 This Heme concentration approaches the range where the Heme-biosensor reaches its maximum activity.
210 (Supplementary Fig. 12). Then, we introduced the AHL and Heme inducers into the system in four distinct
211 states: without any inducers ('00'), with Heme alone ('01'), with AHL alone ('10'), and with both Heme and
212 AHL present ('11'), to assess the consortia's functionality. The output representation of the systems
213 developed in this study was evaluated using bioluminescent signals, as OD₆₀₀ measurements are often
214 impractical in real-world biosensing applications. Unless specified otherwise, bioluminescent signals are
215 used to represent the output throughout the following sections.

216 For both co-cultures, the '00' state (Figs. 3g and 3h, purple curve) remains at a low level, indicating minimal
217 background activity without inducers ('OFF' state). The '10' state (Figs. 3g and 3h, green curve),
218 representing the presence of AHL only, shows a similar response compared to the '00' state in
219 bioluminescence. For the direct regulation co-culture (Fig. 3g), the '11' state demonstrates the highest
220 bioluminescence level, suggesting an additive effect of the inducers. However, the '01' state, which
221 represents the presence of Heme only, displays a response similar to the '11' state in both shape and signal
222 intensity, indicating that Heme alone can elicit a response nearly equivalent to that of both inducers
223 combined.[50], [51], [52]. These results indicate that the direct regulation co-cultures cannot distinguish
224 between the '11' and '10' states. This limitation is likely due to the high background levels of CHL produced
225 within the consortia (Supplementary Table 1) despite using a promoter with inherently low basal activity
226 to regulate CHL synthesis. The decline in signal (after 20 hours) intensity over time is primarily attributed
227 to the consumption or degradation of Heme [54], [55], [56].

228 Compared to the direct regulation and Heme-responsive strain co-cultures (Figs. 3e and 3g), the IFFL strain
229 co-culture (Figs. 3f and 3h) exhibits a more moderated response for the '01' state and a significantly lower
230 signal than the '11' state. Consequently, the '11' state can be distinctly differentiated from other states (Fig.
231 3h). These results confirm the capability of the stable IFFL output signal to control the temporal progression
232 of the input signals. To quantify the CHL concentration produced by the direct regulation circuit (Fig. 3a)
233 and the IFFL network (Fig. 3b), we compared their dynamic response at the final time points (around 20
234 hours) to the one of a Heme-responsive strain induced with 2 μM of Heme and with various concentrations
235 of CHL (Supplementary Fig. 13). For direct regulation circuit (Supplementary Fig. 13A), the '11' state,
236 acting as 'ON' state, corresponds to the response of the Heme-responsive strain at 0.5 μM CHL, while the
237 '01' state, acting as 'OFF' state, corresponds to 0.125 μM CHL. For the IFFL network (Supplementary Fig.
238 13B), the 'ON' and 'OFF' states correspond to approximately 0.125 μM and less than 0.03 μM , respectively.
239 The OD_{600} signals show a similar continuous increase across different states. This consistency suggests that
240 observed differences in output signals are primarily due to the circuits' behavior rather than variations in
241 growth rate (Supplementary Fig. 14). The OD_{600} measurement spans both the exponential and stationary
242 phases of growth. Unless otherwise specified, OD_{600} measurements were provided throughout the
243 subsequent sections to ensure clarity and reproducibility.

244 We then expanded our study to include the Lactate-responsive bacterial biosensor using the same CHL-
245 responsive genetic pathway employed in the Heme-responsive strain (Figs. 3i–3l). Followed a similar
246 experimental protocol to Heme-responsive strain co-culture (Figs. 3i and 3j): Either the IFFL circuit (Fig.
247 3b) or the direct regulation circuit (Fig. 3a) was combined with the Lactate-responsive strain (Fig. 3d) at a
248 1:1 ratio in volume, and added the AHL/Lactate inducer based on four distinct states: without any inducers
249 ('00'), with Lactate alone ('01'), with AHL alone ('10'), and with both Lactate and AHL present ('11'). The
250 experiments were conducted with AHL at a concentration of 2 μM and Lactate at 10 mM. This Lactate
251 concentration approaches the range where the Lactate-biosensor reaches its maximum activity
252 (Supplementary Fig. 15).

253 In the direct regulation co-culture experiments involving Lactate-responsive bacterial biosensors (Figs. 3i
254 and 3k), the '00' state remains low, indicating minimal background activity without inducers. The '10' state,
255 representing the presence of AHL only, shows a similar response compared to the '00' state in
256 bioluminescence. However, a recurring issue is observed where the '11' state, intended to show a response
257 from both AHL and another inducer, does not significantly differ from the '01' state. Conversely, in the
258 IFFL co-culture (Figs. 3j and 3l), the '00' and '01' states show minimal bioluminescence throughout the
259 observation period. The '10' conditions exhibit very little change from the baseline, indicating that neither
260 Lactate nor AHL alone substantially increases bioluminescence in this IFFL co-culture. Similar to the result

261 of Heme-responsive co-culture (Fig. 3h), in the IFFL co-culture scenario (Figs. 3j and 3l), the state '11' state
262 displayed an enhanced response compared to '01', '10', and '00' states. IFFL co-culture further emphasizes
263 its capability to control the temporal progression of different input signals. The OD₆₀₀ signal for the Lactate-
264 responsive strain co-culture is illustrated in Supplementary Fig. 16.

265 Microbial consortium-based biosensors

266 We then developed three distinct consortia configurations to detect Heme and Lactate simultaneously. The
267 first configuration utilized the IFFL strain to generate the CHL shared signal (IFFL Network System, Fig.
268 4a). The second configuration employed the direct regulation strain for CHL production (Direct Regulation
269 System, Fig. 4d). The third configuration relied on supplying the CHL signal externally (External Induction
270 System, Fig. 4g). The data normalized to bioluminescence/ OD₆₀₀ (RLU/ OD₆₀₀) was displayed in
271 Supplementary Fig. 17, and the OD₆₀₀ is shown in Supplementary Figs. 18-20. Each colony's dynamic
272 behavior for the corresponding system is shown in Supplementary Figs. 21-23. Inducers (AHL, Heme, and
273 Lactate) were added simultaneously to the three systems in the beginning of the experiments. The dynamic
274 responses of the IFFL Network System (Figs. 4b, 4c, Supplementary Figs. 24A and 24B), the Direct
275 Regulation System (Figs. 4e, 4f, Supplementary Figs. 24C and 24D), and the External Induction System
276 (Figs. 4h, 4i, Supplementary Figs. 24E and 24F) were measured for more than 40 hours. A threshold level
277 was established to classify the system's states into low and high activity as follows: (1) low state, where
278 there is no consortium activity, which may occur either due to the absence of biomarkers despite a high
279 enable signal (CHL) or the absence of the enable signal even if the biomarker levels are high; and (2) high
280 state, where there is high consortium activity. Accordingly, the threshold was set at the maximum value
281 among five states, including the four states ("00", "01", "10", and "11") when AHL = 0 and the "00" state
282 when AHL = 1. The '00' condition signifies that neither Heme nor Lactate is present, serving as the baseline
283 state; '01' indicates the presence of Lactate alone; '10' represents the presence of Heme alone; and '11'
284 denotes that both Heme and Lactate are added, allowing for the assessment of their combined effect on the
285 system.

286 The dynamic responses of the three systems, measured under conditions of low (Figs. 4b, 4e, and 4h) and
287 high (Figs. 4c, 4f, and 4i) inducer levels (AHL in the case of IFFL Network System and Direct Regulation
288 System, and CHL in the case of External Induction System), illustrate the role of the shared signal as a
289 enable mechanism. Based on the measured results, the thresholds for the IFFL Network and External
290 Induction Systems were observed at AHL=1, Heme=0, and Lactate=0 (Fig. 4c, 4i), while the threshold for
291 the Direct Regulation System occurred at AHL=0, Heme=1, and Lactate=1 (Fig. 4e). Accordingly, the
292 consortia output is engineered to remain at low levels regardless of the activities of the Heme and Lactate-
293 responsive strains when shared signal levels are low (Figs. 4b, 4e, and 4h). When AHL is high in the IFFL
294 Network System and Direct Regulation System, or CHL is high in the External Induction System, the output
295 of all three systems (Figs. 4c, 4f, and 4i) reflects the activity of the input strains, allowing the shared signal
296 to modulate the Heme and Lactate activities by generating a common bioluminescent output signal. In the
297 three configurations, the outputs from the Heme and Lactate-responsive strains are combined to trigger a
298 single readout output, effectively evaluating the consortium's capability to integrate temporally distinct
299 signals through analog summation ($Out_{Total}(t) = Out_{Heme}(t) + Out_{Lactate}(t)$) (Fig. 1b and
300 Supplementary Fig. 25) [51], [53]. This result also suggests the coexistence of the Heme-responsive and
301 Lactate-responsive strains.

302 The IFFL Network System (Fig. 4c) response at AHL=1 can differentiate among the four states ('00', '11',
303 '01', and '10') particularly after 15 hours. In contrast, the Direct Regulation System (Fig. 4f) response at
304 AHL=1 can only distinguish between the '00' and '10' states after 30 hours. The External Induction System
305 (Fig. 4i), however, fails to differentiate between the '00' and '10' states. When the data is normalized by

306 computing the ratio of the measured signal to cell concentration, both the Direct Regulation and External
307 Induction Systems (Supplementary Fig. 17) are able to distinguish between the '00' and '01' states after 10
308 hours. This result aligns with our theoretical model (Eq. 20 in the section 'Mathematical Modelling for
309 Signal Coupling in Microbial Consortia' in Methods). In addition, to evaluate the ability of the three systems
310 to clearly distinguish the '00' state from its threshold level in Figs. 4c, 4f, and 4i, we conducted a statistical
311 analysis to estimate the p-value (Fig. 4j), yielding $p = 0.049$ for the IFFL Network System, $p = 0.419$ for
312 the Direct Regulation System and $p = 0.504$ for the External Induction System. Our calculation was based
313 on comparing the mean bioluminescent signals at the end time point across the '11', '01', '10', and '00' states
314 for three systems. For both the IFFL Network and Direct Regulation Systems (Fig. 4j), the '10' state
315 exhibited the closest to that of the '00' state among the '10', '01', and '11' states, with the Direct Regulation
316 system reaching this point at 43 hours and the IFFL Network System at 46 hours. For External Induction
317 System, the '01' state exhibited the closest to that of the '00' state among the '10', '01', and '11' states. The p-
318 value was determined by conducting an independent two-tailed t-test between the endpoints from the
319 corresponding state and threshold curves in these three systems. We also calculated the fold-change rate in
320 the bioluminescent signal over time by computing the derivative of the output ($dOut/dt$) (Supplementary
321 Fig. 26). The signal derivative of the IFFL Network System shows minimal variation across the four logic
322 states of Lactate and Heme when $AHL = 0$, with significant changes in the other states when $AHL=1$ except
323 for the '00' state. In contrast, the Direct Regulation System displayed high changes in the signal derivative
324 for the '11' state, with values similar to those observed under both low and high AHL conditions
325 (Supplementary Fig. 26). Although the External Induction System exhibited high variability in response to
326 the absence and presence of CHL, it failed to demonstrate a significant change when Lactate was added
327 under conditions of high CHL.

328 Finally, we tested the consortia's robustness by adding initial perturbations in the cell population of bacterial
329 biosensor strains (Figs. 4k and 4l). Specifically, we manipulated the volumes of Heme-responsive strains
330 or Lactate-responsive strains while maintaining constant volumes for the other two strains. The volume of
331 the changing strain (Heme-responsive strains or Lactate-responsive strains) varied from 60 μL to 140 μL ,
332 whereas the volumes for the other biosensor strain and the shared signal consortium were maintained at 100
333 μL , consistent with previous experiments (Supplementary Figs. 27–34). To evaluate the robustness of the
334 three systems, we calculated the Coefficient of Variation (CV) by computing the ratio between the standard
335 deviation and the average signal ('Coefficient of Variation (CV)' in Supplementary Methods). The CV for
336 the IFFL Network System is consistently lower than other systems during the time range of 16 to 42 hours,
337 highlighting the better robustness of the IFFL Network System. Under Heme-responsive strain perturbation,
338 the CV values were 10.7% for the IFFL Network System, 15.2% for the Direct Regulation System, and
339 20.0% and 18.8% for the External Induction System with 2 μM and 0.5 μM CHL, respectively. Similarly,
340 under Lactate-responsive strain perturbation, the CV values were 7.9% for the IFFL Network System,
341 12.8% for the Direct Regulation System, and 15.6% and 10.6% for the External Induction System with 2
342 μM and 0.5 μM CHL, respectively. These values represent the time-average CV across the different
343 conditions observed once the signals begin to reach a steady state (>15 hours). The IFFL Network System
344 demonstrated a 46% improvement in robustness compared to the Direct Regulation System under Heme-
345 responsive strain perturbation, and 90% and 77% improvements compared to the External Induction System
346 with 2 μM and 0.5 μM CHL, respectively. Under Lactate-responsive strain perturbation, the IFFL Network
347 System demonstrated a 72% improvement in robustness compared to the Direct Regulation System and
348 107% and 42% improvements compared to the External Induction System with 2 μM and 0.5 μM CHL,
349 respectively (Supplementary Fig. 35). A similar conclusion regarding the robustness of the three systems
350 against cell fluctuations can be observed from the results of the stochastic simulation (Supplementary Fig.
351 50). Our analytical modeling (Eq. (27) in section 'Mathematical Modelling for Signal Coupling in Microbial

352 Consortia' in Methods) reveals that when strain fluctuations are small (less than 10%), the IFFL-based
353 consortia exhibit enhanced robustness compared to its direct regulation-based counterpart.

354 Coupled consortia for feces diagnostic

355 We also tested our systems with mouse fecal samples to detect Heme and Lactate biomarkers. Heme and
356 Lactate were chosen for their relevance in fecal diagnostics, where their presence may signal potential
357 gastrointestinal health concerns. In this study, we used Lactate at 10 mM and Heme at 2 μ M in the *in vitro*
358 experiments (Figs. 5c, 5d, Supplementary Fig. 36). This Lactate concentration has strategically selected a
359 lower threshold level as a marker for unhealthy conditions in pathological humans [57], [58], [59]. Notably,
360 the summation relationship between these biomarkers underscores their individual significance in the
361 diagnostic process - the presence of either biomarker is sufficient to trigger a response in the system. The
362 procedure for fecal sample preparation is illustrated in Fig. 5a. For all experiments conducted within the
363 fecal sample, we maintained a 1:1 volume ratio between the engineered bacteria consortium sample and the
364 filtered fecal media sample, with the AHL and biomarkers being added before the filtering process. The
365 necessity of the filtering process is explained in Supplementary Fig. 37. In the unfiltered samples, the high
366 and consistent background OD₆₀₀ during the measurements masked the actual dynamics of bacterial growth.
367 Thus, we recommend filtration when detecting small molecules in fecal samples. We followed a recently
368 developed protocol allowing the measurement of green fluorescent signals from fecal samples [60].

369 First, we validated the consistency of the Direct Regulation and IFFL networks in filtered fecal samples
370 (Fig. 5b), confirming alignment with the results observed in our *in vitro* experiments. The output signal of
371 the direct regulation circuit (the same genetic circuit used *in vitro* experiments from Fig. 2b) increased
372 continuously over time, failing to reach a saturation point within the 15-hour timeframe (Fig. 5b, black
373 curve). By contrast, the IFFL network from Fig. 2a displayed a relatively stable expression within the fecal
374 sample throughout the measurement period (Fig. 5b, red curve). The output signal of the IFFL network is
375 higher than that of the negative control (Fig. 5b, blue curve, engineered bacteria circuit containing only the
376 antibiotic and plasmid copy number). Compared to *in vitro* experiments (Fig. 2d), the expression levels for
377 both co-cultures are notably reduced. The OD₆₀₀ signal is shown in Supplementary Fig. 38.

378 We examine our consortia in three steps. The first step included a Heme-responsive strain with the direct
379 regulation or IFFL strains within the filtered fecal sample media (Supplementary Figs. 39-40). The second
380 step included a Lactate-responsive strain with the direct regulation or IFFL strains within the filtered fecal
381 sample media (Supplementary Figs. 41-42). In both steps, we observed a behavior similar to *in vitro*
382 experiments. Finally, we tested the consortia, including the three strains (the same consortium design used
383 *in vitro* experiments from Fig.4a): IFFL, Heme, and Lactate-responsive strains with the absence and
384 presence of AHL. Based on the corresponding states, inducers (AHL, Heme, and Lactate) were introduced
385 at the beginning of the experiment. We then examined these coupled consortia over 40 hours to detect and
386 monitor the presence of Lactate and Heme in humanized fecal samples (Figs. 5c, 5d, Supplementary Fig.
387 36). In the presence of AHL (Fig. 5d), the '11' state initially reflects the behavior of the '10' state for the
388 first 25 hours. During this phase, the output signal reflects the Heme-responsive strain's reaction. Then,
389 starting around the 30-hour mark, the '11' state began to mirror the dynamics of the '01' condition,
390 representing the Lactate-responsive strain's behavior. Therefore, the '11' signal is able to successfully reflect
391 the multiple consortium-based input signals, aligning the dynamic of each individual input and providing a
392 more robustness output in the fecal sample for diagnostic purposes (Supplementary Fig. 43). Additionally,
393 we tested the consortia's robustness in response to minor perturbations in the populations of the individual
394 bacterial biosensor strain (Supplementary Figs. 44). The IFFL Network System shows better robustness
395 compared to the Direct Regulation System. In this experiment, the data is presented as the measured
396 bioluminescence signal without normalization by cell concentration, reflecting strategies common in

397 practical applications where measuring OD₆₀₀ is often not feasible. The OD₆₀₀ signal is shown in
398 Supplementary Fig. 45. Additionally, we provide results (Supplementary Fig. 46) from inflamed acute
399 colitis murine model fecal samples that were inherently bleeding demonstrating that our Heme sensor can
400 detect inflammatory fecal samples. We used an acute colitis murine model induced by dextran sodium
401 sulfate (DSS) (Methods). The bioluminescent response observed in the DSS-treated samples with CHL
402 indicates the sensor's sensitivity to pathological states, validating the sensor's application in biologically
403 relevant scenarios of inflammation.

404 Discussion

405 In this study, we demonstrate that synthetic bacterial biosensors within consortia can be coupled through
406 shared signaling molecules. Compared to systems where CHL is either externally supplied or internally
407 produced by the direct regulation circuit, the IFFL network ensures consistently low-level CHL signaling,
408 thereby effectively coupling the individual bacterial sensors in a consortium. Through computational
409 simulations and experimental analysis, we have identified that systems under IFFL control exhibit enhanced
410 robustness with respect to variations and perturbations in cell concentration. We also observe indications
411 of coexistence between the Heme-responsive and Lactate-responsive strains (Figs. 4c and 4f). In the IFFL
412 Network System configuration, the output of the synthetic consortia regulated by the IFFL exhibits reduced
413 dependence on cell concentration within the consortium, which is advantageous in environments where
414 maintaining a consistent cell concentration is challenging.

415 Our insights mark significant progress in developing large, synthetic multicellular systems. By harnessing
416 this method to simultaneously initiate biosensors that detect multi-markers within fecal samples, we
417 highlight its capacity to operate in resource-limited environments, demonstrating its potential for future
418 medical applications and scaling up systems. Our approach is versatile and can be adapted to monitor
419 various biomarkers in feces, as well as other healthcare environments such as urine and sweat. However,
420 for each application, the detection window and time intervals would need to be adjusted accordingly.

421 Multi-marker cell-based biosensors with a single output and a single chamber simplify the biosensor system
422 by reducing the complexities associated with multi-chamber biosensors and photodetector configurations.
423 By contrast, biosensors equipped with multiple chambers tend to be expensive and highly power-consuming,
424 thereby limiting their applicability in many biomedical and environmental contexts. For instance, an
425 ingestible capsule has been recently developed for the *in-situ* detection of labile inflammatory biomarkers
426 [61]. This system measures the activity of bioluminescent bacteria-based biosensors within two separate
427 chambers. However, adding more chambers to measure additional biomarkers would result in an
428 impractical increase in capsule size and hinder practical application. When this capsule requires the
429 measurement of multiple biomarkers, the solution lies in designing multi-marker biosensors with a single
430 output. Similarly, a remote detection system for buried landmines using bacterial biosensors has been
431 developed [3]. If this system were to measure different types of explosive materials, the most viable
432 approach involves designing multi-marker biosensors with a single output. Furthermore, in both of these
433 examples, due to the challenge of real-time signal normalization with respect to biosensor cell concentration
434 (OD₆₀₀), unlike our system, where the measured signal is much less dependent on biosensor cell
435 concentration, our system is expected to provide more precise and reliable data.

436 Another potential application of our synthetic IFFL network is in gene expression studies. A stable output
437 regulation facilitates accurate tracking of these temporal changes, ensuring a reflection of the true biological
438 state. Similarly, in therapeutic-based living cells [62], stabilized transient responses can play a pivotal role
439 in optimizing treatment outcomes. Consistent drug production, be it in the context of bacterial cancer
440 therapies or engineered probiotics for treating inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) [63], is significantly

441 important. The stable transient response of our network can be incorporated as a drug-release module within
442 these therapeutic cells, guaranteeing a uniform drug dose over the entire treatment duration.

443 Our stabilization IFFL circuit can also be useful in metabolic engineering. It can enhance the production
444 yield of targeted chemicals within synthetic bio-production pathways. These pathways frequently
445 necessitate the removal of endogenous genes linked to cell growth and upkeep. However, this gene deletion
446 ultimately leads to low growth rates [64], significantly impacting the eventual yield of the desired bio-
447 product. Therefore, achieving a stable response through low-level expression of these endogenous genes
448 could address this challenge.

449 Methods

450 Chemicals and Biological Samples

451 Sodium Lactate (L-lactate), hemin (ferric chloride heme or Heme), acyl-homoserine lactone 3OHC14:1-
452 HSL (CHL), and acyl-homoserine lactone 3OC6HSL (AHL) were used as inducers (Sigma–Aldrich,
453 Germany). A stock solution of Heme was prepared by dissolving hemin powder in 1 M NaOH (Sigma–
454 Aldrich, Germany) to a concentration of 25 mM, diluting with double distilled water to a final concentration
455 of 100 μ M, and sterilizing with a 0.22 μ m polyethersulfone (PES) filter. All the chemicals were of the
456 highest analytical grade. The experiments were conducted with AHL at a concentration of 2 μ M, Lactate
457 at 10 mM, and Heme at 2 μ M.

458 Ethics

459 All mouse work was in accordance with protocols approved by the local Technion, Israel, The Institutional
460 Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) under approval numbers: IL-151-10-21 and IL-135-09-22.

461 Human donor feces were collected from a healthy male individual volunteer with informed consent,
462 according to Rambam Health Care Campus (RAMBAM) medical center IRB approval NCT03167398.

463 Mice Humanization

464 4-5 weeks-old Germ-Free (GF) C57BL/6 mice (males and females) from the Technion colony were used.
465 Mice were housed and maintained in a GF care facility and were provided with food and water ad libitum;
466 they were exposed to a 12:12 h light-dark cycle at room temperature. Human stool sample were frozen at
467 -80°C before processing. Humanized mice were generated by orally gavaging GF C57BL/6 mice with 200
468 μ L of a fecal suspension prepared from a single healthy human donor, in which 1 gram of feces was
469 suspended in 10 mL of sterile PBS (1:10 w/v) [65].

470 Acute DSS-Induced Colitis Mouse Model

471 For acute DSS-induced colitis in humanized mice, male and female mice were co-housed separately, and
472 then treated with 3% (w/v) DSS in their drinking water for 8 days [66]. The control animals were
473 administered distilled water. Fecal samples for analysis were collected on day 8, coinciding with the end of
474 the treatment and the day of sacrifice. Daily assessments included monitoring body weight, stool
475 consistency, and blood in the rectum or stool. Throughout the experiments, close attention was paid to
476 monitor any distress responses exhibited by the mice: mice with a 20% decrease in body weight,
477 immobility, or an extreme reaction to touch, were excluded from the experiments.

478 Feces Suspension

479 Mice fecal samples (30-50mg) were flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen and then stored at -80°C [67], and
480 suspended in sterile PBS in 1ml/100mg feces, centrifuged at 4,500xg for 15 minutes, and supernatants were
481 collected as the nonfiltered sample. If needed, filtered using the Medical Millex-VV Syringe Filter Unit,

482 0.22 μm , PVDF membrane or Corning sterile 96-well filter plate with polystyrene insert, 0.2 μm , PVDF
483 hydrophilic membrane (Corning Incorporated, Kennebunk, ME, USA). When filtered with a plate, the
484 samples were separated for 200 μL in each well, centrifuged at 4,500 $\times\text{g}$ for 15 minutes, and collected. All
485 the steps were done on ice.

486 Bacterial Strains

487 The *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) 10 β strain from New England Biolabs (Beverly, MA) was used to construct
488 all plasmids, and in the kinetics experiments (genotype: araD139 D (ara-leu) 7697 fhuA lacX74 galK (W80
489 D (lacZ) M15) mcrA galU recA1 endA1 nupG rpsL (StrR) D (mrr-hsdRMS-mcrBC)). Chemically and
490 electroporation-competent *E. coli* cells were prepared using standard protocols [68], [69].

491 Plasmid Construction

492 All the plasmids in this work were constructed using basic molecular cloning techniques [69] or Gibson
493 Assembly [70]. Detailed plasmid maps, combinations, and genetic parts are provided in the Supplementary
494 Information. The plasmids were modified by restriction digests, performed using New England Biolabs
495 (Beverly, MA) restriction endonucleases and FastDigest restriction enzymes (ThermoFisher Scientific Inc.,
496 USA). For ligation, T4 DNA ligase and Taq polymerase were used (New England Biolabs, Beverly, MA).
497 PCR was performed with a Bio-Rad S1000 thermal cycler with dual 48/48 fast reaction modules.
498 Oligonucleotides were synthesized by Integrated DNA Technologies (Coralville, IA)—the manipulation of
499 different parts (i.e., replacing promoters or genes) using the same restriction sites. Gibson assemblies were
500 carried out using New England Biolabs (Beverly, MA) NEBuilder HiFi DNA assembly cloning kit.
501 Plasmids were transformed into *E. coli* using a standard heat shock protocol [69] or a MicroPulser
502 electroporator [68]. Colony PCR screening was carried out using forward and reverse primer pairs. Positive
503 clones were sequence-verified. According to the manufacturer's instructions, plasmids were isolated with
504 Promega Wizard Plus SV Minipreps DNA Purification Systems (Promega Corporation, Madison, WI,
505 USA). The Macrogen Sequencing Service performed DNA sequencing (Macrogen Europe, The
506 Netherlands).

507 Bacterial Culture

508 *Escherichia coli* strains were stored as glycerol stocks at -80°C and then grown at 37°C in a Shel
509 Laboratories SSI5 shaking incubator at 250 rpm in 5 mL of Lysogeny broth (LB-Miller) medium (Fisher),
510 supplemented with carbenicillin (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), kanamycin (30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), or chloramphenicol (34 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$).
511 Overnight cultures were diluted 100-fold into 5 mL of fresh LB medium with antibiotics and regrown with
512 shaking at 37°C and 250 rpm for 0.5 h ($\text{OD}_{600} \approx 0.1$).

513 For the M9+0.4% glucose media experiment (Supplementary Fig. 10), the cells were overnight cultured in
514 LB and were diluted 1:50 into fresh M9+0.4% glucose medium [1 \times M9 Salts (Sigma-Aldrich, M6030), 2
515 mM MgSO_4 , 100 μM CaCl_2 , 0.4% glucose, 0.1% casamino acids, 50 mg/l thiamine]. The cultures were
516 incubated for 1hr for the M9+0.4% glucose media experiment or 30 min for other experiments at 37°C with
517 250 rpm and then measured with a plate reader. GFP signals were read at 15-minute intervals using a
518 Synergy H1 monochromator-based multimode microplate reader with continuous shaking at 500 rpm and
519 a constant temperature of 37°C . GFP fluorescence was quantified by excitation at a wavelength of 485 nm
520 and emission at a wavelength of 516 nm. Unless otherwise stated, all experiments were repeated with three
521 replicants. GFP values were measured in arbitrary relative fluorescence units (RFUs), and the normalized
522 signals were calculated by dividing these values by the OD_{600} .

523 Feces Preparation for Experiments

524 Centrifuged feces supernatants were collected and mixed with various concentrations of
525 Heme/Lactate/AHL/CHL or their combinations and filtered as the states needed. When non-filtered, only
526 top-layer supernatant was collected and supplemented with inducers. Either filtered or non-filtered mice
527 feces supernatants were prepared and complemented with carbenicillin (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), kanamycin (30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$),
528 or chloramphenicol (34 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$).

529 Microplate Reader Kinetics Experiments

530 Culture aliquots (150 μL) were transferred into wells of 96-well plates, mixed with various concentrations
531 of Heme/Lactate/AHL/CHL or their combinations diluted in 150 μL of LB/sterile PBS, or for fecal
532 supernatants experiments. The inducers were included in the sample. Luminescence and green fluorescent
533 protein (GFP) signals were read at 15- or 20-min intervals using a Synergy H1 monochromator-based
534 multimode microplate reader with shaking at 500 rpm and a constant temperature of 37°C for GFP
535 experiments and 23°C for luminescence. The luminescence signal was measured at 490 nm. GFP
536 fluorescence was quantified by excitation at a wavelength of 485 nm and emission at a wavelength of 516
537 nm. Luminescence and GFP values were measured in arbitrary relative fluorescence units (RFU) and
538 luminescence units (RLUs), and the normalized signals were calculated by dividing these values by the
539 optical density (OD_{600}) of the culture measured at 600 nm. Unless otherwise stated, experiments were
540 conducted in triplicate.

541 Experiments using FACS

542 Flow cytometry analyzer voltages were adjusted using CyExpert 2.2 software to ensure that both maximum
543 and minimum expression levels could be accurately measured under the same voltage settings, which were
544 consistently maintained throughout all experiments, including repeated runs. GFP was excited with a
545 488 nm laser, and each FACS run acquired 10,000 events with an abort rate below 2%. Fluorescence, along
546 with forward and side scatter measurements, was recorded using CyExpert 2.2 software. The geometric
547 median of the gated fluorescence distributions was calculated using MATLAB, and fluorescence values,
548 expressed in arbitrary units (arb. units), were based on the geometric medians from three independent
549 experiments. Cells were first gated based on forward scatter (FSC-A) and side scatter (SSC-A) to identify
550 the major viable population, typically comprising over 90% of the total cell population. Fluorescence
551 intensity was then measured for the gated population to assess the relevant markers. Flow cytometry data
552 from one representative experiment is provided in Supplementary Fig. 8 and Supplementary Table 1.

553 Analog Signal Control in Biosensor Consortia

554 Under certain conditions, where the concentration of the total shared signal distributed across the entire
555 consortia ($S_T = \sum_{i=1}^M S_i$, where S_i is the shared signal for each consortium) is lower than that of the total
556 cell concentration ($S_T \ll \sum_{i=1}^M N_i$), can facilitate a coupling among the diverse cells. This, in turn, reduces
557 the influence of cell concentration within each consortium on the overall output signal $Out \propto \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M N_i f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^M N_i}$ (Fig.
558 1a and Supplementary Fig. 1). Furthermore, if the shared signal is inducible, it can serve as an enable signal
559 for externally regulating the system output (Fig. 1b). This control signal functions as a conditional gate:
560 when the signal is at a high level, it permits the transmission of the biosensor's response, effectively
561 "enabling" the system's output ($S_T = High, Out = f, t > t_0$). Conversely, it prevents signal transmission
562 when the control signal is in a low level state ($S_T = Low, Out = 0, t < t_0$). The realization of a circuit
563 incorporating an enabled control signal is comparatively complicated in the analog domain compared to the
564 digital domain. In digital circuits, enabling can be accomplished using an AND logic gate. In analog circuits,
565 e.g., biosensors, the implementation involves a circuit that computes the minimum between the activity of

566 the enable signal and the analog response of the input signal; $MIN\{g(Enable), f(In)\}$ (i.e.,
567 $MIN\{Low, f\} = 0$, and $MIN\{High, f\} = f$) (Supplementary Fig. 1). On one hand, the ON level must be
568 lower than the total cell concentration to couple the cells effectively (Methods). On the other hand, the ON
569 level of the enable signal should exceed the activity of each biosensor to ensure proper computation of the
570 minimum operation. Thus, programming the correct ON level of the shared signal is challenging. Enabling
571 is also considered a foundational step toward achieving member coordination within consortia. Without
572 proper coordination, temporal misalignments between cellular activities may give rise to significant
573 consequences, encompassing undesired cellular responses [14], [15].

574 Conceptual and Mathematical Examination of the IFFL Network Dynamics

575 In the diagram of the IFFL network (Fig. 2a), the molecule x activates both molecules y and z with rates
576 α_1 and ρ , respectively. Furthermore, in this normalized equation, molecule y inhibits molecule z with a
577 dissociation constant of k and a Hill coefficient of n . The degradation rates of z equals γ_2 , of y equals γ_1 .
578 The Ordinary Differential Equation (ODE) for molecule concentration of z and y are given by:

$$579 \quad \dot{z} = \rho \frac{x}{1 + \left(\frac{y}{k}\right)^n} - \gamma_2 \cdot z \quad (1)$$

$$580 \quad \dot{y} = \alpha_1 \cdot x - \gamma_1 \cdot y \quad (2)$$

581 For the direct regulation (Fig. 2b), the production rate of z is α_0 and the degradation rates of z equals γ_0 .
582 The ODE in this case for molecule z is represented as:

$$583 \quad \dot{z} = \alpha_0 \cdot x - \gamma_0 \cdot z \quad (3)$$

584 We begin by illustrating this stability response's conceptual underlying in the network's dynamic
585 performance. We use k_n to illustrate the comparison between the repression pathway to the activation
586 pathway, $k_n = \frac{k \cdot \gamma_1 \cdot \rho}{\alpha_1 \cdot \gamma_2}$. Our mathematical analysis of the IFFL network (Eqs. (1) and (2)) demonstrates three
587 different behaviors using a step function input for x :

- 588 1. Fold change detection: Within this interval, the initial rise in output (illustrated by the green curve
589 $k_n = 0.01$) stems from the direct activation of z by x (through activation pathway A in Fig. 2a).
590 This is followed by a decrease brought about by y 's time-delayed repression. As repression initiates
591 with an increase in y levels, a strong decrease ensues, resulting in a pulse-like pattern of behavior.
592 When $k_n \ll 1$, the robust repression enables the system to revert to its baseline state following the
593 initial stimulus. This behavior is known as perfect adaption.
594
- 595 2. Enduring stability: In this interval, a stable output arises from the equilibrium between activation
596 and repression. As shown in Fig. 2c, where $k_n = 1.5$ (red curve) and $k_n = 0.5$ (blue curve), the
597 IFFL network accelerates the response speed compared to a directly regulated network, leading to
598 an earlier reach of a steady state. In the IFFL, while maintaining the network parameters constant,
599 we varied the parameter k_n to explore its impact on network dynamics.
600
- 601 3. For a large value of $k_n > 1$, the activation will be the dominant process, resulting in a behavior
602 similar to that of the directly regulated network.

603 **As conclusion:** a trade-off arises in the IFFL network dynamics; strong repression typically results in
604 an accelerated, pulse-like response, while a stable output is usually achieved with weaker repression.

605 We selected the IFFL for this work because of its ability to maintain stability ($k_n > 1$) over extended
606 periods.

607 Mathematical Modelling for Signal Coupling in Microbial Consortia

608 To enhance coupling within the consortia system, we formulated a strategy employing a common signaling
 609 molecule, S , among various bacterial strains. This study assumes that S signal is coupling only two
 610 engineered bacterial consortia, each designed for a distinct biosensor function. These biosensors are
 611 customized to detect specific input signals (I_{n1} and I_{n2}) while also being responsive to the shared signaling
 612 molecule S . Our mathematical dynamic model utilizes cooperative interactions across the consortium and
 613 is given by:

618 Here, E_i denotes the concentration of a transcription factor that can interact with S across both biosensor
 619 types, while SE_i represents the fraction of the transcription factor bound to S . Furthermore, P_i (where $i =$
 620 $1,2$) indicates the production concentration triggered by I_{n1} and I_{n2} , respectively. With K_{mi} and K_i as the
 621 dissociation constants for the respective reactions, the result is the production of Z_i (Z_1 and Z_2) molecules
 622 (Supplementary Fig. 47). At the steady-state, we can write:

$$623 \quad SE_i = \frac{S \cdot E_i}{K_{mi}} \quad (8)$$

624 The total transcription factor level of each respective bacterial strain reveals:

$$625 \quad E_{Ti} = E_i + SE_i \quad (9)$$

626 Here, we assumed that the total level of the transcription factor E_{Ti} is uniformly distributed across the same
 627 strain. The total level of the shared signal across the system is described by:

$$628 \quad S_T = S + N_1 \cdot SE_1 + N_2 \cdot SE_2 \quad (10)$$

629 with N_1 and N_2 describe the bacterial population of each respective strain.

630 Assuming $K_{m1} = K_{m2}$ and $E_{T1} = E_{T2}$, the system dynamics can be simplified as:

$$631 \quad \begin{cases} E_T = E + SE & (11) \\ S_T = S + (N_1 + N_2) \cdot SE & (12) \end{cases}$$

632 Combining these equations yields an expression for SE :

$$633 \quad SE^2 - SE \left(E_T + \frac{S_T}{N_1 + N_2} + \frac{K_m}{N_1 + N_2} \right) + \frac{S_T}{N_1 + N_2} \cdot E_T = 0 \quad (13)$$

634 The solution is:

$$635 \quad SE = \frac{E_T + \frac{S_T}{N_1 + N_2} + \frac{K_m}{N_1 + N_2} - \sqrt{\left(E_T + \frac{S_T}{N_1 + N_2} + \frac{K_m}{N_1 + N_2} \right)^2 - 4 \frac{S_T}{N_1 + N_2} \cdot E_T}}{2} \quad (14)$$

636 We can approximate this equation as:

$$637 \quad SE = E_T \cdot \frac{S_T}{E_T \cdot (N_1 + N_2) + S_T + K_m} \quad (15)$$

638 Considering the dynamics described by Eqs. (6) and (7), P_1 and P_2 are functions of I_{n1} and I_{n2} ; therefore
 639 $P_i = f_i(I_{ni})$. At the steady state, the output Z_i is given by the solution of the equation $Z_i = \frac{SE \cdot P_i}{K_i}$. Thus, the
 640 output Z can be described as:

$$641 \quad Z = SE \cdot \left(\frac{N_1 \cdot f_1(I_{n1})}{K_1} + \frac{N_2 \cdot f_2(I_{n2})}{K_2} \right) \quad (16)$$

642 Using the above approximation, the total signal Z becomes:

$$643 \quad Z = E_T \cdot \frac{S_T}{E_T \cdot (N_1 + N_2) + S_T + K_m} \cdot \left(\frac{N_1 \cdot f_1(I_{n1})}{K_1} + \frac{N_2 \cdot f_2(I_{n2})}{K_2} \right) \quad (17)$$

644 This expression suggests that the output signal is coupled by the shared signaling molecules S_T ; the
 645 interplay between N_1 and N_2 is smoothed by their combined effect $(N_1 + N_2)$. The shared signal introduces
 646 an extra constraint on the system, consequently limiting its degree of freedom. Importantly, the signals
 647 $f_1(I_{n1})$ and $f_2(I_{n2})$ should be similar; otherwise, signal Z will be dominated by one of them.

648 On the other hand, for independent biosensors devoid of shared signaling, the output Z_{ind} is given by:

$$649 \quad Z_{ind} = N_1 \cdot f_1(I_{n1}) + N_2 \cdot f_2(I_{n2}) \quad (18)$$

650 In the Z_{ind} expression, the total signal is influenced by N_1 and N_2 individually. Variations in one
 651 population directly impact the total output signal.

652 For system analysis in Eq. (17), we considered various conditions, including both high and low levels of
 653 shared signal S_T . Starting with high levels of S_T : $S_T + K_m \gg E_T \cdot (N_1 + N_2)$, the total signal shown in Eq.
 654 (17) is approximated by:

$$655 \quad Z = E_T \cdot \frac{S_T}{S_T + K_m} \cdot \left(\frac{N_1 \cdot f_1(I_{n1})}{K_1} + \frac{N_2 \cdot f_2(I_{n2})}{K_2} \right) \quad (19)$$

656 The total output signal depends on the two strains of consortium separately, which is similar to the
 657 expression of the Z_{ind} in Eq. (18). In both scenarios, the output isn't adjusted by the bacterial population
 658 counts N_1 and N_2 . However, for precise values of $f_1(I_{n1})$ and $f_2(I_{n2})$ and subsequent estimation of I_{n1} and
 659 I_{n2} , normalization by $N_1 + N_2$ is needed.

660 On contrast, for small S_T , meaning $S_T + K_m \ll E_T \cdot (N_1 + N_2)$ in Eq. (17) is approximated to:

$$661 \quad Z = \frac{S_T}{(N_1 + N_2)} \cdot \left(\frac{N_1 \cdot f_1(I_{n1})}{K_1} + \frac{N_2 \cdot f_2(I_{n2})}{K_2} \right) \quad (20)$$

662 The output signal is already normalized by the total cell number $N_1 + N_2$. Consequently, there is no
 663 necessity to divide the measured signals by the total cell concentration when calculating the correct signals.
 664 The output normalization is simplified because the shared signal introduces an additional constraint, thereby
 665 confining the system with S_T .

Eq. (20) also suggests that the system's output is more robust against fluctuations in bacterial population ratios. To further investigate this robustness and understand the potential effects of individual consortium variations, we postulated exponential growth for both bacterial strains, introducing a small difference in the growth rate specifically for the strain N_2 .

$$N_1 = N_0 e^{\mu \cdot t} \quad (21)$$

$$N_2 = N_0 e^{(\mu + \Delta\mu) \cdot t} = N_1 e^{\Delta\mu \cdot t} \quad (22)$$

In case that $\Delta\mu \cdot t \ll 1$, we can approximate:

$$N_2 = N_1 \cdot (1 + \Delta\mu \cdot t) \quad (23)$$

For the output, Z_{ind} is given by:

$$Z_{ind} = N_1 \cdot (f_1(I_{n1}) + f_2(I_{n2})) + N_1 \cdot \Delta\mu \cdot t \cdot f_2(I_{n2}) \quad (24)$$

When S_T is large, and assuming that $K_1 = K_2 = K$. The Eq. (19) can be approximated as:

$$Z = \frac{E_T}{K} \cdot \frac{S_T}{S_T + K_m} \cdot N_1 \cdot (f_1(I_{n1}) + f_2(I_{n2}) + f_2(I_{n2}) \cdot \Delta\mu \cdot t) \quad (25)$$

The output Z depends on N_1 and the error term $f_2(I_{n2}) \cdot \Delta\mu \cdot t$. However, if the S_T is small, the Eq. (20) is approximated as:

$$Z = \frac{S_T}{2 \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\Delta\mu}{2} \cdot t\right)} \cdot \left(\frac{f_1(I_{n1})}{K_1} + \frac{f_2(I_{n2})}{K_2} + \frac{f_2(I_{n2})}{K_2} \cdot \Delta\mu \cdot t\right) \quad (26)$$

For $\frac{\Delta\mu}{2} \cdot t \ll 1$, we can approximate the term $\frac{1}{1 + \frac{\Delta\mu}{2} \cdot t} \approx 1 - \frac{\Delta\mu}{2} \cdot t$. Substituting the latter term into Eq. (26)

and assuming $K_1 = K_2 = K$, we obtain:

$$Z = \frac{S_T}{2 \cdot K} \cdot \left(f_1(I_{n1}) + f_2(I_{n2}) + \frac{\Delta\mu}{2} \cdot t \cdot (f_2(I_{n2}) - f_1(I_{n1}))\right) \quad (27)$$

The output solution is independent of the concentration of strain population N_1 or N_2 . Moreover, the error is much smaller than the error in the Eq. (25).

The results indicate that outputs for systems with lower S_T values are independent of individual strain concentrations, thereby offering a more robustness and normalized output compared to systems with larger S_T . Therefore, shared signal presents a method for coupled responses within a consortia, leading to outputs with greater precision and reduced calibration needs when utilized in devices.

We then performed simulations for consortia dynamics, including two biosensors. Specifically, we investigated the condition with and without a shared signal. The population dynamics and behavior of the input signals are detailed in Supplementary Figs. 48 and 49. Notably, Supplementary Fig. 50 demonstrates that when a shared signal couples the consortium, the final output, represented by the aggregation (sum) of the two biosensors, exhibits reduced sensitivity to fluctuations in cell population. Additionally, we evaluated the output signal using Eq. (17) for different S_T levels. There's a distinct reduction in noise, shown in Supplementary Fig. 51, when $S_T + K_m \ll E_T \cdot (N_1 + N_2)$ compared to the conditions with higher levels of S_T , where $S_T + K_m \gg E_T \cdot (N_1 + N_2)$.

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699 Data Availability

700 All data used in this study is available in GitHub (<https://github.com/LSB2/2025-Engineering-Coupled->
701 [Consortia-Based-Biosensors-for-Diagnostic.git](https://github.com/LSB2/2025-Engineering-Coupled-)) All relevant data are also available from the authors upon
702 request. The raw data generated in this study are provided in the Supplementary Information and Source
703 Data file.

704 Code Availability

705 Computer code is available from GitHub under <https://github.com/LSB2/2025-Engineering-Coupled->
706 [Consortia-Based-Biosensors-for-Diagnostic.git](https://github.com/LSB2/2025-Engineering-Coupled-).

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922 Author Contributions Statement

923 R.H., V.K., and R.D. designed the study. R.H., V.K. and M.H. performed *in vitro* experiments and collected
924 data. R.H. , V.K. and R.Z. performed fecal sample experiments and collected data. R.D. and R.H. associated
925 models and simulations. R.H., V.K., and R.D. wrote the manuscript. N.G.-Z. supervised the study and
926 provided experimental assistance. All authors analyzed the data, discussed the results, and wrote the
927 manuscript.

928 **Competing Interests Statement**

929 The authors declare no competing interests.

930 **Figure Legends/Captions**

931

932 *Figure 1 Coupled biosensors through shared signaling molecules. (a) Different biomarker inputs (In_1 and In_2*
 933 *represent the Heme and Lactate in our study) trigger two bacterial biosensor consortia, each with its own cell*
 934 *concentration (N_1 and N_2). When the system is activated by the input signals (In_1 and In_1), only part of N_1 and N_2*
 935 *(indicated in green color) contribute to the overall output (Out). The red and gray curves are illustrative and used to*
 936 *represent the effects of input coupling within the consortia. The coupling consortia (red curve) is shown to enhance*
 937 *the robustness and reliability of the output compared to the uncoupled consortia (gray curve). These curves do not*
 938 *depict actual experimental responses. (b) A coupled consortia ($S_T < N_1 + N_2$) with shared signaling molecules (S_T*
 939 *represents CHL in this study) that is distributed across the entire consortia $S_T = S_1 + S_2$. This shared signal controls*
 940 *the activity of two different bacterial biosensors ($f_1(In_1, t)$ and $f_2(In_2, t)$ represent the activities of Heme and Lactate*
 941 *in our study). Under changes in the cell concentration ($N_1 + \Delta N_1$ and $N_2 + \Delta N_2$), this coupled consortium consortia*
 942 *shows a more robust output ($Out = Out_1 + Out_2$) compared to an uncoupled consortium. Figures created with*
 943 *BioRender.*

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946 *Figure 2 Development of Incoherent Type-1 Feedforward Loop (IFFL) circuit. (a) Schematic diagram and genetic*
 947 *circuit for incoherent type-1 feedforward loop (IFFL). (b) Schematic diagram and genetic circuit for direct regulation.*
 948 *(c) Simulation results are described the normalized Eq. (1)-(3) (Methods). The IFFL network is represented by curves*
 949 *in different colors corresponding to various k_n values: $k_n = 1.5$ (red), $k_n = 0.5$ (blue), and $k_n = 0.01$ (green). The*
 950 *direct regulation circuit is depicted by the black dashed curve. The remaining parameters are $\alpha_0 = \alpha_1 = \gamma_1 = \rho =$*
 951 *$\gamma_0 = \gamma_2 = n = 1$ (Methods). (d) Plate reader experiments show the dynamics for the IFFL network and direct*
 952 *regulation circuit for about 30 hours, represented by red and black curves, respectively. The gray dashed line indicates*
 953 *the average value of the IFFL network between 2 to 15 hours. Unless further stated, the shaded area around the curve*
 954 *indicates the standard deviation of three replicants in the measurements and the measure of center represents the*
 955 *mean. The inset figure shows the optical density (OD_{600}) of cells in the IFFL network and direct regulation circuit.*
 956 *Source data are provided as a Source Data file. Figures (a) and (b) created with BioRender.*

957

958 *Figure 3 Whole-cell biosensors using Direct Regulation and IFFL network co-cultures. (a-d) Basic genetic circuits:*
 959 *(a) Direct regulation circuit, (b) Stability output IFFL network, (c) Heme-responsive strain, and (d) Lactate-*
 960 *responsive strain. (e-h) Dynamic responses and schematic diagram of Heme-responsive strain co-cultures with direct*
 961 *regulation (e and g) or IFFL network (f and h). For both consortia, the response to combinations of AHL and Heme*
 962 *is monitored: '00' (purple curve) signifies no inducers, '01' (red curve) indicates Heme only, '10' (green curve)*
 963 *represents AHL only, and '11' (blue curve) indicates the presence of both AHL and Heme. (i-l) Dynamic responses*
 964 *and schematic diagram of Lactate-responsive strain co-cultures. The direct regulation co-culture response to AHL*
 965 *and Lactate is shown in i and k, while the IFFL network's response is in j and l. The conditions tested are analogous*
 966 *to those in e-h, with '00' as the no inducers, '01' for Lactate, '10' for AHL, and '11' for both inducers present. Source*
 967 *data are provided as a Source Data file. Figures (a) - (j) created with BioRender.*

968

969 *Figure 4 Microbial consortium-based biosensors. (a-c) Representations of the IFFL Network System in vitro. (a)*
 970 *Schematic gene circuit diagrams for IFFL Network System. (b-c) Dynamic response in the absence of AHL inducer*
 971 *(b) compared to its presence (c). (d-f) Representations of the Direct Regulation System. (d) Schematic gene circuit*
 972 *diagrams for the Direct Regulation System. Dynamic response in the absence of AHL inducer (e) compared to its*
 973 *presence (f). (g-i) System representations with externally added CHL (External Induction System). The empty strain*
 974 *containing only the antibiotic and plasmid copy number. (g) Schematic diagram of the gene circuit for the External*
 975 *Induction System. (h) Dynamic response in the absence of CHL inducer compared to (i) its presence. The threshold*
 976 *(red horizontal line) for the systems is based on the average curve from the three replicates. And the threshold is set*
 977 *as the maximum value observed among the following five states: the four states ("00," "01," "10," and "11") when*
 978 *AHL = 0, and the "00" state when AHL = 1. (j) Mean bioluminescent signals at their threshold level across states '11',*

979 '01', '10', and '00' for three systems: IFFL Network System (IFFL), Direct Regulation (DR), and External Induction
 980 System. Each state's mean value is shown in a bar chart, with individual replicates represented as small circles on
 981 each bar. The four states are represented in distinct colors: '11' (blue), '01' (red), '10' (green), and '00' (purple). Error
 982 bars indicate the standard deviations of the three replicates. (k-l) The coefficient of variation (CV) for the IFFL
 983 Network System (red square curve), Direct Regulation System (black dotted curve), and External Induction System
 984 (yellow triangle curve for $CHL = 2 \mu M$ and orange stars curve for $CHL = 0.5 \mu M$) under perturbations from the
 985 Heme-responsive strain (k) or Lactate-responsive strain (l). Source data are provided as a Source Data file. Figures
 986 (a), (d) and (g) created with BioRender.

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988

989 Figure 5 Coupled consortia for feces diagnostic. (a) Procedure for fecal sample experiments: (1) Collection of fecal
 990 samples from humanized mice. (2) Suspension of fecal samples in sterile PBS, followed by centrifugation to collect
 991 the supernatants. (3) Adding the inducers to the supernatants and subsequent filtration of the mixture. (4) Mixing of
 992 the bacterial co-culture with the filtered supernatants, with measurements taken using a microplate reader. (b)
 993 GFP/OD₆₀₀ response dynamics of the IFFL network (IFFL, red curve), the direct regulation (DR, black curve), and
 994 the negative control circuit (NC, green curve) within fecal samples. (c-d) Dynamics response of the IFFL Network
 995 System in the absence (c) and presence (d) of AHL within the filtered fecal sample. Source data are provided as a
 996 Source Data file. Figures (a) created with BioRender.